

CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION IN THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF KEY FINDINGS

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Abstract

Purpose – Based on the premise that shifting from a linear system of resource consumption to a circular model could play a critical role in paving the way for a sustainable future, this paper provides an analysis of the existing literature on the topic of consumption and production in the the circular economy.

Methodology/approach – Following the methodology of a systematic review, this paper analyzed a total of 59 papers related to the topic of consumption and production in the circular economy.

Findings – It was found that the core of circular consumption and production models is that all product or product-service systems in the closed-loop supply chain have the potential to be redesigned and used in the subsequent product life cycle, thus adding value to resources or materials.

Research limitations/implications – Understanding circular consumption and production can enable businesses to decouple their profit from their resource consumption so that they become resilient and sustainable. This review has limitations, primarily due to its qualitative study classification is inherently influenced by researcher bias.

Practical implications – These findings strengthen the importance of creating an environment that enables the relevant stakeholders of a community to work together in supply chains.

Originality/value – A new explanatory model is proposed that explains how communities can enable the circular economy.

Key words: circular economy, sustainability, resource efficiency.

1. Introduction

The dissonance between the finite amount of available resources and the seemingly infinite human needs has long been studied in the scientific literature. Modern societies and their embedded economic systems have proven incapable of dealing with natural resource scarcity in a satisfactory long-term manner. The disparity between resources and human desires is expected to widen as we anticipate significant changes in the near future (Scheel, Aguiñaga & Bello, 2020, Lakatos et al, 2020). These issues are not new, in fact, academics have long been aware of them and have linked them to the threat posed by climate change. The contemporary consumerism that predominantly characterizes production and consumption models in high-income countries does not seem to be an economic model capable of simultaneously addressing the increasing population and its anthropogenic load. As a result, shifting from the current, ecologically unsustainable patterns of consumption and production to new, more sustainable ones is seen as an essential development objective with broad implications. In this context, the circular economy has begun to gain momentum as a solution to these problems (Giampetro & Funtowicz, 2020).

The essential feature of circular economy consumption and production is that all goods must circulate in a closed system. Biological and/or technical nutrients used in the manufacture of goods are designed to either safely re-enter the biosphere or alternatively to recirculate in the system at highest level of quality possible without re-entering the biosphere (UNEP, 2006). As a result, the proposal for a circular economy of production and consumption includes a "closed loop economy" based on "redesign"

thinking. Murray and colleagues (2017) proposed that biomimetics—the use of natural system structure and function to inform industrial processes—optimizes sustainable production in the circular economy.

Despite empirical evidence (Rada, Cioca & Ionescu) that the circular economy can optimize resource use, no theoretical review has been conducted to integrate consumption and circular production in a comprehensive model. Only 19% of studies defining the circular economy, according to Kirchherr and colleagues' research from 2017, took consumption and production into account. Although business and consumer acceptance were mentioned as topic areas in Van Eijk's (2015) prior analysis, which focused on the causes and challenges to the circular economy, the outlook was fairly wide. Geissdoerfer (2017) also wrote a review that focused on the connection between sustainability and the circular economy but did not include any discussion of how things are manufactured and consumed.

Therefore, this paper aims to fill a gap in the literature by pursuing two main goals. The first one aims at highlighting key characteristics of circular consumption and production and incorporating them into a theoretical model. The second goal is to develop a new descriptive model that integrates the 10Rs principles (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Refuse, Rethink, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, R-cover) to facilitate circular consumption and production in communities.

2. Methodology

A systematic review's purpose is to synthesize all empirical data on a specific topic that meet a set of pre-defined criteria in order to generate new knowledge or models. The essence of any theoretical review is to use a replicable methodology while trying to identify all studies that could meet the eligibility criteria in order to provide a concise presentation of the research question investigated. The literature research was conducted on the WoS search engine. The following types of works were excluded:

- Articles that do not present new ideas;
- Papers presented at conferences,
- Technical reports, and book chapters;
- Articles that do not define data sources or in which data collection is unclear;
- Articles that do not address consumption/production in the circular economy;
- Papers published before 2010.

The methodological approach applied in this paper is depicted in Figure 1. The final sample included 59 articles.

Figure 1. Methodological approach

3. Findings

The final sample was classified into conceptual papers, case studies and exploratory papers. Firstly, the conceptual paper showed us that circular consumption and production have no universally accepted definitions. However, a vast majority of the proposed models assume that all products and services systems in the supply chain can be redesigned and used as raw materials or resources in the next new product life cycle, thereby creating added value (Camacho-Otero, Boks & Pettersen, 2018). The case studies analysis allowed us to observe that although waste is considered a resource in circular production and consumption, not all waste can be recycled or reused, in part because of the infrastructure the physical and thermodynamic limitations. The environment's capacity to absorb trash from the economy is crucial, yet the majority of papers published so far either fail to take this limitation into account or do not address it effectively (Peng et al., 2019, Sehnem et al., 2019). Finally, from the exploratory studies, we found that there are untapped opportunities for economic growth through circular economy, beyond costs saving generated by recycling and reusing. According to the exploratory approaches, any new demand insertion in the circular flow of investment or consumption is expected to have a multiplier impact, resulting in increased investment (Wieser & Troger, 2018, Iacovidou et al., 2017).

Based on these findings, the model depicted in Figure 2 was created. Since no theoretical model identified in the sample of studies addressed the issue from this perspective, the model describes how circular consumption and production can be facilitated in communities using the 10R principles identified in Kircher's (2017) paper and the supporting mechanisms for implementing circularity presented in Yang, Zhou and Xu (2014).

Figure 2. Proposed model for facilitating circular consumption and production in communities

The model also contains two main support means for the promotion of circular consumption and production. The assumption that infrastructure can facilitate the adoption of circular consumption and production is based on the idea that technological advancement and the circular economy are inherently linked. Even if the role of technology in micro-level initiatives (such as education or awareness campaigns) is less obvious, at the community level it becomes clear that technology is needed. For example, industrial symbiosis implies collaborative technological innovation for waste recovery. On the

other hand, regulatory mechanisms mostly involve national legislation and local decisions to support circular consumption and production. This concept also encompasses financing schemes for circular businesses, their accessibility, and the interactions with public authorities in terms of information exchange and financial regulation issues (Yang, Zhou & Xu, 2014, Păcurariu et al., 2021)

4. Research implications and limitations

From a practical standpoint, this paper highlights the importance of creating an environment that enables businesses and entities to work together in supply chains. For instance, the growth of clusters would enable these businesses to convert their unwanted externalities into materials that can be used by other organizations. The local institutions and governments supporting these businesses would benefit from the sustainable consumption and production of resources. In order to construct closed-loop systems, businesses can establish profitable partnerships with their suppliers, clients, and other stakeholders in a circular community (Ghisiellini et al., 2017). Nevertheless, particular industries are better suited to circular initiatives than others because recycling their resources is rather straightforward. For primary industries, such as iron, steel, and aluminum incentives to reduce waste in closed-loop systems may suffice. Secondary industries, such as solar and wind energy technologies or battery manufacturing, and biotechnological materials, will inevitably need to be reassessed in terms of recycling potential and life cycle performance (Cammilleri, 2017).

Moreover, the coronavirus revealed the fragility of the economic system, based on profit and continuous consumption of resources. Since this crisis has led to a reduction in commercial activity, the revival of economic activity requires the commitment of businesses to rely on economic recovery laws based on sustainability (Cifiuntes-Haura, 2022). Therefore, understanding circular consumption and production can enable businesses to decouple their profit from their resource consumption so that they become resilient and sustainable.

This review has limitations, primarily due to its qualitative nature. Despite the fact that the study selection process was documented to ensure replicability and transparency, study classification is inherently influenced by researcher bias. The inclusion and exclusion criteria were detailed in the paper to address this issue. Another consideration is the decision to examine only articles published in journals, which excludes the consideration of gray literature, which could make an important contribution to the review's objectives. Furthermore, there is a chance that the literature review we conducted overlooked several articles, that are relevant to the research. This limitation could be due to the way the database query was built, as we chose publications based on the literal use of the concepts circular economy, production, and consumption.

5. Conclusions

This systematic review provided an analysis of the existing literature on the topic of circular consumption and production. The core of circular consumption and production models is that all products or product-service systems in the closed-loop supply chain have the potential to be redesigned and used as raw materials or resources in the subsequent product life cycle, thus adding value to resources or materials (Yang, Zhou & Xu, 2014, Blomsma & Brennan, 2027). However, in order to further implement circular consumption and production, the coordination and cooperation of multiple closed-loop supply chain systems is essential, in order to optimize reuse and recycling potential and capture additional value by integrating all supply chain activities.

References

Blomsma, F. and Brennan, G.

2017

The emergence of circular economy: a new framing around prolonging resource productivity. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 21(3), pp.603-614.

Camacho-Otero, J., Boks, C. and Pettersen, I.N.

2018.

Consumption in the circular economy: A literature review. *Sustainability*, 10(8), p.2758.

Camilleri, M. A.

2017

Corporate sustainability and responsibility: creating value for business, society and the environment. *Asian Journal of Sustainability and Social Responsibility*, 2(1), 59-74.

Camilleri, M. A.

2018

Closing the loop for resource efficiency, sustainable consumption and production: A critical review of the circular economy. *International Journal of Sustainable Development*, 21(1-4), 1-17.

Cifuentes Faura, J.

2022

Circular economy and sustainability as a basis for economic recovery post-COVID-19. *Circular Economy and Sustainability*, 2(1), 1-7.

Geissdoerfer, M., Savaget, P., Bocken, N.M. and Hultink, E.J

2017

'The circular economy –a new sustainability paradigm?', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 143, pp.757–768.

Giampietro, M., and Funtowicz, S. O.

2020

From elite folk science to the policy legend of the circular economy. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 109, 64–72.

Ghisellini, P., Cialani, C. and Ulgiati, S.

2016

A review on circular economy: the expected transition to a balanced interplay of environmental and economic systems. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 114, 11-32.

Iacovidou, E., Millward-Hopkins, J., Busch, J., Purnell, P., Velis, C., Hahladakis, J. N., ... and Brown, A.

2017

A pathway to circular economy: Developing a conceptual framework for complex value assessment of resources recovered from waste. *Journal of cleaner production*, 168, 1279-1288.

Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., and Hekkert, M.

2017

Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 127,221–232.

Lakatos, E. S., Yong, G., Szilagyi, A., Clinci, D. S., Georgescu, L., Iticescu, C., & Cioca, L. I.

2021

Conceptualizing core aspects on circular economy in cities. *Sustainability*, 13(14), 7549.

Murray, A., Skene, K., and Haynes, K.

2017

The circular economy: an interdisciplinary exploration of the concept and application in a global context. *Journal of business ethics*, 140(3), 369-380.

Pacurariu, R. L., Vatca, S. D., Lakatos, E. S., Bacali, L., and Vlad, M.

2021

A critical Review of EU Key Indicators for the Transition to the Circular Economy. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(16), 8840.

Peng, S., Yang, Y., Li, T., Smith, T. M., Tan, G., and Zhang, C.

2019

Environmental benefits of engine remanufacture in China's circular economy development. *Environmental science & technology*, 53(19), 11294-11301.

Rada, E. C., Cioca, L. I., and Ionescu, G.

2017

Energy recovery from Municipal Solid Waste in EU: Proposals to assess the management performance under a circular economy perspective. In *MATEC Web of Conferences* (Vol. 121, p. 05006). EDP Sciences.

Scheel, C., Aguiñaga, E., and Bello, B.

2020

Decoupling economic development from the consumption of finite resources using circular economy. A model for developing countries. *Sustainability*, 12(4), 1291.

Sehnm, S., Jabbour, C., Pereira, F., and Jabbour, L.

2019

Improving sustainable supply chains performance through operational excellence: circular economy approach. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 149, 236-248.

Tseng, M., Chiu, A. S., Liu, G., and Jantaralolica, T.

2020

Circular economy enables sustainable consumption and production in multi-level supply chain system. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 154, 104601.

UNEP

2006

Circular Economy: An Alternative Model for Economic Development, United Nations Environment Programme, Paris, France [online] <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Portals/24147/scp/nap/circular/pdf/prodev-summary.pdf>

Van Eijk, F.

2015

Barriers & drivers towards a circular economy. Literature review. *Acceleratio*: Naarden, 1-138.

Wieser, H., and Tröger, N.

2018

Exploring the inner loops of the circular economy: Replacement, repair, and reuse of mobile phones in Austria. *Journal of cleaner production*, 172, 3042-3055.

Yang, Q. Z., Zhou, J., and Xu, K.

2014

A 3R implementation framework to enable circular consumption in community. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Development*, 5(2), 217